

Geoinformatic-based Foundations for Landscape Character Assessment Falasarna, Crete, Greece

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Introduction

- Landscape Character Assessment (LCA): systematic approach to describe & map landscape diversity
- Supports sustainable landscape planning and management

Study Area: Falasarna, Crete

- Area of Interest (AOI)
40 sq kilometers
- Total population ~1150 people
- Main settlements Platanos (pop 900 p)
and Sfinari (pop 100 p)

Study Area: Falasarna, Crete

- Ecologically, agriculturally, and culturally rich landscape
- High historical, archaeological, and economic value
- Coastal, agricultural, tourism-related and archaeological features

Excavations begun in 1986

70's

80's

ancient years, Hellenistic period
(323-30 BC)

90's

current

Research Objectives

- Develop a geoinformatics-based LCA framework
- Generate geospatial basemaps as foundation
- Classify Land Description Units (LDUs) and Landscape Character Types (LCTs) to capture landscape character
- Perform visibility analysis to capture landscape quality

Methodology Overview

- Desktop analysis → geospatial basemaps
- Spatial analysis techniques (landform-landcover classification, object-based supervised classification of satellite imagery, combinatory analysis of thematic basemaps)
- Delineation of Land Description Units (LDUs), fieldwork validation and assessment, delineation of Landscape Character Types (LCTs)
- Visibility analysis

Data & Basemaps (geology, soil, natura areas)

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Data & Basemaps (streams, streets, archaeology)

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Data & Basemaps (relief, landform, viewshed)

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Data & Basemaps (CORINE, Pléiades, historic landcover)

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Land Description Units (LDUs) through landform-landcover combinatory analysis

Landform

- Plain (PL), flat or gently undulating topography, lying at the base of rising slopes, at any altitude.
- Lowland (L), land generally lying < 200m above sea level, topography undulating or rolling.
- Hills (H), elevated tracts of land, between 200-600m above base level, topography rolling.
- Uplands (U), elevated tracts of land, between 600-1200m above base level, topography mostly rolling.
- Deep Valleys (DV), valleys at least as deep as they are wide, with vertical or near-vertical slopes on large parts of the valley sides, often including cliffs and rock outcrops.

Landcover

- olive groves
- bare rock
- broad-leaved forests
- beaches
- urban fabric
- complex cultivates patterns - greenhouses
- grasslands - sclerophyllous vegetation - sparsely vegetated areas - pastures

Land Description Units (LDUs) through landform-landcover combinatory analysis

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Landscape Character Types (LCTs) through fieldwork refinement & assessment

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Survey	Date: Polygon ID:					Comments
1	Geology/soil	Dominant (75-100%)	Prominent (50-75%)	Apparent (10-50%)	Insignificant	
2	Land use	Dominant (75-100%)	Prominent (50-75%)	Apparent (10-50%)	Insignificant	
3	Settlement	Dominant (75-100%)	Prominent (50-75%)	Apparent (10-50%)	Insignificant	
4	Topography	Undulating	Gently Undulating	Rolling	Flat	
5	Woodland / shrub cover	Extensive / Large	Regular / Medium	Linear	Scattered/ Small	
6	View	Filtered	Framed	Open	Exposed	
7	Field Pattern	Regular	Open Landscape	Recurring pattern		
8	Intensity of Management	High	Medium	Low		
9	Natural Features / Other features					
10	Free text / Comments					

Polygon ID:		0%-100%
1	Lush – Rich vegetation, including olive groves and Mediterranean flora.	
2	Vibrant – Area full of life, with diverse flora and fauna.	
3	Raw – The coastline and rocky landscapes maintain a rugged and natural beauty.	
4	Dramatic – Cliffs, hills, and a striking coastline make for breathtaking scenery.	
5	Arid – Sun-soaked rocky terrain contrasts with cultivated fields and olive groves.	
6	Harmonious – The balance between the sea, traditional agriculture, and nature is striking.	
7	Wild – Remote and relatively untouched areas still exist, retaining their natural charm	
8	Ancient – Home to historical ruins, including the ancient city/port of Falasarna, adding depth to the landscape.	
9	Sacred – Echoes of ancient Greek history and mythology give the place a special significance.	
10	Serene – Especially at sunset, the region exudes tranquility and peace.	
11	Fierce – The exposed coastline faces the open sea, with strong winds and waves shaping the environment.	
Polygon ID:		0%-100%
1	Aesthetic (beauty of the landscape, coastline, and natural scenery)	
2	Cultural (traditions, local customs, and way of life)	
3	Tourism (importance for visitors, attractions, eco-tourism, etc.)	
4	Recreational (hiking, swimming, water sports, local events, etc.)	
5	Natural (ecological value, biodiversity, unique species, etc.)	
6	Economic (agriculture, tourism, fishing, local businesses, etc.)	
7	Historical (rich past, ancient sites, traditional settlements, etc.)	
8	Social activities (community gatherings, festivals, local interactions, etc.)	
9	Natural Features / Other features	
10	Free text / Comments	

Landscape Character Types (LCTs) through fieldwork refinement & assessment

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- 14 survey locations
- 9 merged landscape character types
 - Beachfront and agricultural coastal lowlands (mainly greenhouses)
 - Rocky shrubland lowlands
 - Rocky shrubland hills
 - Lowland olive groves
 - Terraced agriculture and natural vegetation on hills
 - Lowland settlement
 - Hilltop settlement
 - Forested lowlands
 - Forested hills

Visibility analysis

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Visibility analysis

Tveit, M., Ode, Å., & Fry, G. (2006). Key concepts in a framework for analysing visual landscape character. *Landscape Research*, 31(3), 229–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01426390600783269>

Visibility analysis (connectivity – complexity – naturalness)

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Visibility analysis (disturbance – visual scale – historicity)

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Landscape character (core area)

- olive groves
- Falasarna beachfront with its agricultural land (mainly greenhouses)
- hilltop settlement of Platanos village with its surrounding terraced agricultural areas
- small landscape patches of rocky shrublands in both lowlands and hills

Provisioning ES: olive groves, greenhouse cultivations

Cultural ES: archaeological heritage, tourism, recreation, outdoor activities

Landscape character (secondary area)

- large areas of rocky shrublands in lowlands and hills
- small lowland settlement of Sfinari village with its beachfront
- limited crops and greenhouses
- small olive grove
- forested areas

Provisioning ES: olive grove, greenhouse cultivations

Landscape quality

Core area

- higher values of visual scale, especially in the lowland and beachfront zones
- resulting in a landscape of higher preference and perceived quality
- spatially integrated but also complex area in terms of land use patches
- with cultural significance
- with relatively low naturalness
- with a high degree of human intervention.

Secondary area

- it is characterized by extensive patches of natural land cover
- fewer artificial elements
- less general visual disturbance
- it is less spatially complex and less coherent area
- with significantly lower cultural attributes
- lower values of visual scale, except at its northern edge where higher naturalness values contribute to increased landscape quality.

Conclusions

- Geoinformatics-based LCA framework that integrates GIS, remote sensing & field validation
- Landscape character: it captured through LCTs delineation
- Landscape quality: it captured through visibility analysis
- Landscape diversity: 9 distinct character types capture ecological, agricultural & cultural richness
- Landscape distinct areas: Core area = high cultural/visual value but lower naturalness; Secondary area = higher naturalness but less cultural visibility
- Ecosystem services: Trade-offs between provisioning (olive groves, greenhouses) and cultural values (heritage, tourism)

Future Work

- Engage stakeholders for applicability (through TOPIO project)
- Expand to other Mediterranean regions

Thank you for your attention!

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TOWARDS DEMOCRATIC LANDSCAPE OBSERVATION THROUGH
GEOINFORMATICS AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

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